

Paper 1

INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION & COMPUTATION TECHNOLOGY (ICCT) – AN OVERVIEW

P. S. Aithal¹ & Madhushree L. M.²

¹College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²Research Scholar, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore-
575 001, India

E-mail : psaithal@srinivasgroup.com

Abstract

Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) and Nanotechnology (NT) are recently identified Universal technologies to solve problems related to the basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings. In this paper, the possibilities of using ICCT and its underlying ten most important emerging technologies like Artificial intelligence, Big data & business analytics, Cloud computing, Digital marketing, 3D printing, Internet of Things, Online ubiquitous education, Optical computing, Storage technology, and Virtual & Augmented Reality are explored. The emerging trends of applications of the above underlying technologies of ICCT in the primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary industry sectors of the society are discussed, analysed, and predicted using a newly developed predictive analysis model. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of such technologies to fulfill the desires of human beings to lead luxurious and comfort lifestyle from various stakeholders point of views are identified and discussed. The paper provides an overview on the potential applications of ICCT in various primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary industries.

Keywords : ICCT, Universal technology, Emerging trends, Information science & technology, Industry sectors.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Technology is defined as an application of science and is used to solve different problems in society with an intention to make human life comfortable and enjoyable. Many technologies have been identified as General-Purpose Technologies due to their abilities to solve problems in many sectors in the society. Such technologies are used by many branches of engineering to solve or simplify the problems of those fields [1]. General Purpose Technologies' (GPT) are developed due to the ability of killer applications in solving problems in many industrial sectors. Examples for such killer applications which have been converted into GPT's are steam engine, railroad, interchangeable parts, electricity, semiconductor electronics, material handling, mechanization, control theory (automation), the automobile, the computer, the Internet, Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), and Nanotechnology (NT). But out of the above killer application technologies, only two technologies further emerged as Universal technologies of the 21st century. In this paper, we have considered and discussed the major underlying technologies of ICCT and their emerging

trends of applications on the primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary industry sectors of the society using a newly developed predictive analysis model [2].

2. UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES OF ICCT :

Recently it is argued that information generation, communication, processing, storing, and retrieval are the parts of a single system called Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) and is considered as an integrated version of Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Computer Technology (CT). It is also observed that ICCT shows all the three characteristics of GPT : Pervasiveness, Growth, and Innovation opportunity. In the 21st century, ICCT is grown and spread its roots to all industries and industry sectors from A to Z due to its pervasiveness property [2]. The Improvement and Innovation spawning properties of Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) as general purpose technology are created major stake holding areas including Artificial intelligence, Big data & business analytics, Cloud computing Technology, Digital marketing Technology, 3D printing Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Online Ubiquitous education & Training Technology, Optical computing Technology, Information Storage technology, and Virtual & Augmented Reality.

Table 1 : ICCT underlying technologies, their objectives, and ultimate goal

S. No	Underlying Technologies of ICCT	Objectives	Ultimate Goal
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Performing by thinking and doing things better than human beings	Ideal artificial brain & connecting brains with computers
2	Big data and Business Analytics	Developing effective information using hidden patterns, unknown correlations, market trends, and customer preferences to help organizations for making better business decisions	Ideal Business prediction
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Using computer infrastructure at cost effective and optimum level from ubiquitous location	Ideal Computer [3]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	Ubiquitous mobile business and e-marketing using digital and internet technology	Ideal Business [4, 5]
5	3D printing Technology	Preparing three dimensional structures from a digital file. This is achieved using additive processes using less material than traditional manufacturing methods	Ideal Production of components & Devices
6	Internet of Things (IoT)	Interconnection and integration of the physical world and the cyber space remotely to control the	Ideal interconnection & Control

		devices from distance	
7	Online Ubiquitous Education & Training	Education for everybody irrespective of location, age, economic level using technology	Ideal education system [6, 7]
8	Optical Computing Technology	High speed data processing	Ideal Computers [8, 9]
9	Information Storage Technology	Huge amount of information storage in a small region using suitable technology	Ideal storage system
10	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Virtual reality is an immersion experience which gives the physical world feelings	Ideal virtual experience [10]

Table 2 : Basic needs and ideal solutions

S. No.	Basic Needs of the society	Best solutions	Supporting Technologies
1	Nutritious Food	Artificial Food	Cellular agriculture, 3D food printing, Artificial photosynthesis etc.
2	Drinking water	Potable water	Nanotechnology
3	Transportation	Zero cost transportation	Solar technology, Energy storage technology, Nanotechnology, Virtual reality
4	Energy	Free energy from renewable sources	Solar technology, Energy storage technology, Nanotechnology
5	Shelter	Low cost, safe, and durable shelter called smart home	Nanotechnology, IoT, 3D printing
6	Education	Ubiquitous education	Wireless technology, Multimedia, and Internet technologies
7	Health	Quick solutions to all health related deceases	AI, IoT, Nano & Bio Technology
8	Long life	Prolonged life span of individuals	Bio-technology, Genetic engineering,

3. ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES IN INDUSTRY SECTORS :

ICCT has many applications in the many Industries and Industry sectors. Almost all Industries and industry sectors belonging to Primary, Secondary, Tertiary, and Quaternary Industry Sectors are basically supported by and get benefits from ICCT. In this section, some of the applications of ICCT in different industry sectors are discussed [11].

3.1. ICCT Underlying Technologies in Primary Industry Sector :

Industries and Industry sectors in primary sector are expected to get benefit from ICCT in to produce raw materials for other sectors. Some applications of ICCT in Primary Industry Sector are listed in table 3.

Table 3 : Some applications of ICCT in Primary Industry Sector

S. No.	Underlying technologies of ICCT	Applications in Primary Industry Sector
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	AI based autonomous robots to handle essential agricultural tasks such as harvesting crops at a higher volume and faster pace than human labourers, to monitor crop and soil health, to study the environmental impacts on crop yield such as weather changes, precision farming, yield management etc. are seen as a weapon in doubling farmer income in near future [12].
2	Big data and Business Analytics	Smart farming, Precision agriculture, Big data analytics on reduction in fertilizer, cost savings, yield optimization, Seed quality management, Accurate crop prediction, Automated agriculture, Environmental awareness, Risk management, Food safety and spoilage prevention, etc. [13-14]
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Smart agriculture in which Agriculture-Cloud and IT offers expertise service to farmers regarding cultivation of crops, pricing, fertilizers, disease detail method of cure to be used etc. Scientists working at Agriculture research stations can add their discoveries, suggestions regarding modern techniques for cultivation, usage of fertilizers, can obtain cultivation history of the region etc. [15-17]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	E-marketing of agricultural products, Digital advertisements on global reach, Engage and interact with target audience and customer base [18].
5	3D printing Technology	Used in agriculture, forestry, and fishing industries for 3D printing based Food fabrication, Wood fabrication, recycling of fishing nets & ropes etc. [19-22].
6	Internet of Things (IoT)	Smart agriculture model, Environmental Monitoring and Control, Improving Agricultural Operations, Waste management, For fresh agricultural products, etc. [23-25].
7	Online Ubiquitous Education & Training	Agricultural education, Farm management, [26]
8	Optical Computing Technology	Precision fish farming, High speed processors for information processing
9	Information Storage Technology	Enhanced data storage for high speed processing.
10	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Agriculture farm management using Augmented reality, AR and VR for Cultivating the Garden etc. [27]

4. ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES IN SECONDARY INDUSTRY SECTOR :

Industries and industry sectors in secondary sector are expected to get benefit from ICCT for manufacturing the goods (Table 4).

Table 4 : Some applications of ICCT in Secondary Industry Sector

S. No.	Underlying technologies of ICCT	Applications in Secondary Industry Sector
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Intelligent manufacturing, Smart manufacturing, Industrial automation leading to Industry 4.0 etc. [28]
2	Big data and Business Analytics	Industrial big data analytics and cyber-physical systems, Cleaner manufacturing, Supply chain management, Cyber manufacturing, fault prediction for shop floor scheduling, [29]
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Opportunities, challenges, and determinants of cloud computing adoption in manufacturing, Enhancing the product realization process with cloud-based design and manufacturing, Ubiquitous manufacturing system based on Cloud computing technology, and Cloud computing services usage in manufacturing processes. [30-34]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	Digital technology and E-business in manufacturing sector, and use of Web analytics for digital marketing etc. [35-37]
5	3D printing Technology	3D technology is used for additive manufacturing, Smart manufacturing, 3-D printing in the construction industry, and is considered as an industrial revolution for 21 st century. [38-42]
6	Internet of Things (IoT)	Internet of Things as roadmap for manufacturing, IoT based manufacturing for emerging Industry 4.0 concept of manufacturing. [43-46]
7	Optical Computing Technology	Next-generation optics manufacturing technologies, Reconfigurable manufacturing systems. [47-48]
9	Information Storage Technology	Digital manufacturing for enhanced storage with small, reliable, and cheaper systems. [49]
10	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Virtual reality in automotive manufacturing, Augmented Reality in Aerospace Manufacturing, etc. [50-54]

5. ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES IN TERTIARY INDUSTRY SECTOR :

Industries and industry sectors in tertiary sector called services sector are expected to get benefit from ICCT. Table 5 lists some of the services sector gets benefit from underlying technologies of ICCT.

Table 5 : Some applications of ICCT in Tertiary Industry Sector

S. No.	Underlying technologies of ICCT	Applications in Tertiary Industry Sector
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Artificial Intelligence technology is used in many areas of service industry sector including tourism, telecommunications, citizen services, Banking sector for loan decisions, retail sector, etc. [55-59]
2	Big data and Business Analytics	In Supply chain management, Banking sector, Tourism sector, health sector, financial & insurance sector, fashion industry, [60-64].
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Financial service industry, Education industry, Security industry, Brokering service, Healthcare, Gaming industry, Supply-chain industry, Telecommunication industry, [65-67]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	Digital Marketing and customer relationship in all kind of industry including hotel industry, tourism industry, health industry etc. [68-69]
5	3D printing Technology	Health sciences, Forest industry, [70-71]
6	Internet of Things (IoT)	Service innovations are possible using IoT. Smart city services including Tourism, Healthcare, Telecommunication, Logistics, Transportation, Retail, etc. [72-76]
7	Online Ubiquitous Education & Training Technology	Education industry, Library services, Retail banking, Healthcare services, etc. [77-79]
8	Optical Computing Technology	Optical technology based high speed computers are essential in future Retail industry sectors, Logistics & Supply chain industry sectors, Telecom industry sector, Information security industry, etc. [80-81]
9	Information Storage Technology	All services industry sectors where huge amount data and information related to the business are to be stored and retrieved at high speed in small device.
10	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Education & Training, Tourism, Travel industry, Finance, etc. [82-84]

6. ICCT UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES IN QUATERNARY INDUSTRY SECTOR :

Table 6 : Some applications of ICCT in Quaternary Industry Sector

S. No.	Underlying technologies of ICCT	Applications in Quaternary Industry Sector
1	Artificial Intelligence Technology	Artificial intelligence technology is used in IT industry to automate software development, code writing, software testing, IT security monitoring etc. [85-89]

2	Big data and Business Analytics	Big data based IT-enabled services can be developed and improved. [90-92]
3	Cloud Computing Technology	Cloud computing based IT as a service, Cloud computing-software as a service. Impact on mobile software development using cloud computing etc. [93-95]
4	Digital Business & Marketing	Supply of software products, implementation support and maintenance using online digital technologies.
5	Internet of Things (IoT)	Using Internet of Things for innovations in software development and providing IT Enabled services efficiently. [96]
6	Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality	Education and training in software industry using virtual reality and augmented reality model.

7. CONCLUSION :

It is observed that Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) is having applications in many areas of society to solve problems of society as Universal general purpose technology of 21st century. The ICCT underlying technologies are expected to support various business organizations in many industry sectors. The emerging trends of applications of the above underlying technologies of ICCT in the primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary industry sectors of the society are reviewed, discussed, and analysed.

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